

Structural relaxation of phosphate glasses

M. Chromčíková^{*1,2}, B. Hruška³, M. Liška^{1,2}

¹ VILA – Joined Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: maria.chromcikova@tnuni.sk, marek.liska@tnuni.sk)

² VILA, FunGlass, A. Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: maria.chromcikova@tnuni.sk, marek.liska@tnuni.sk)

³ Central Laboratories, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: branslav.hruska@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

The structural relaxation of three compositional series of PbO-WO₃-P₂O₅ glasses with composition $(0.5 - x / 2) \text{PbO} \cdot x\text{WO}_3 \cdot (0.5 - x / 2) \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$, $x = 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$; $0.5 \text{PbO} \cdot x\text{WO}_3 \cdot (0.5 - x) \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$, $x = 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$; and $(0.5 - x) \text{PbO} \cdot x\text{WO}_3 \cdot 0.5 \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$, $x = 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$ was studied by thermomechanical analysis [1, 4]. The relaxation was described using a mathematical model based on the stretched exponential relaxation function with relaxation time proportional to actual viscosity. The viscosity dependence on thermodynamic temperature and fictive temperature was expressed by Mazurin's approximation [2, 3, 5]. The relaxation parameters dependence on the glass composition was studied. It was found that the modulus is increasing with increasing amount of WO₃ in all glasses. On the contrary, the width of the spectrum of relaxation times is decreasing with increasing amount of WO₃ in all studied glasses.

Keywords: Phosphate glasses, Structural relaxation, Viscosity, Glass transition.

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